

From Code to Production: A Quantitative Analysis of SaaS Characteristics for MaaS Development

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Abstract. This paper explores the conceptual transfer of Software-as-a-Service (SaaS) principles to the emerging domain of Manufacturing-as-a-Service (MaaS). While SaaS has become a mature and widely adopted model in software distribution, its structured application within cloud-based manufacturing remains underexplored. Through a bibliometric analysis of 65 academic publications retrieved from Scopus, this study identifies ten recurring SaaS characteristics, spanning infrastructure (e.g., cloud deployment and data security), service operations (e.g., performance monitoring and SLAs), and user/business interface (e.g., subscription pricing and UX design). Their relevance to MaaS contexts is examined through a content mapping procedure and synthesized into a three-layer capability framework. The results reveal a growing yet fragmented body of research addressing this translational potential, with conceptual gaps in areas such as service integration, pricing models, and modularity. A visual framework is proposed to support the adaptation of SaaS logic into MaaS environments, offering a structured foundation for future research on digital servitization and industrial service ecosystems.

Keywords: Software as a Service, Manufacturing as a Service, Cloud Computing, Cloud Manufacturing, Bibliometric Assessment.

1 Introduction

Cloud computing has introduced significant changes in information technology by redefining how digital interactions and resource management are conducted, with broad implications for users and enterprises (Kiswani et al., 2021). This transformation has reshaped business models, operational strategies, and user engagement, fostering scalable, data-driven, and service-oriented ecosystems across sectors.

Within the context of Industry 4.0, Manufacturing-as-a-Service (MaaS) has emerged as a transformative production model that applies cloud computing logic to physical manufacturing. MaaS enables the virtualization and remote access of production resources—such as machines, robotics, and fabrication capabilities—facilitating on-demand use, improved capacity utilization, and reduced fixed investment costs (Wu et al., 2013; Hasan & Starly, 2020). It aligns closely with Industry 4.0 trends by integrating

cyber-physical systems, the Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT), and real-time analytics to support distributed, flexible production (Pivoto et al., 2021; Kang et al., 2016).

Despite this growing interest, MaaS remains conceptually and operationally under-developed compared to other cloud-based service models. In contrast, Software-as-a-Service (SaaS) has achieved wide adoption as a delivery model for managed applications hosted over the Internet using single-instance, multi-tenant architectures (Nadeem, 2022). SaaS systems maximize scalability and usability while minimizing infrastructure ownership and maintenance. Operating through subscription or pay-per-use models, they offer standardized user experiences and continuous system improvement (Yasiukovich & Haddara, 2020).

The rise of cloud computing has been supported by both technological and economic developments—such as the growth of large-scale data centers and declining communication costs. SaaS has played a central role in shifting software delivery models by reducing technical barriers and altering cost structures (Yasiukovich & Haddara, 2020).

Given these differences in maturity, this study investigates whether and how established SaaS traits can inform the development of MaaS frameworks. While SaaS and MaaS operate in distinct domains—digital functionality versus physical production—their reliance on cloud infrastructure, modular architectures, and usage-based access offers a conceptual bridge for theoretical and practical integration.

To explore this bridge, we conduct a bibliometric analysis of 65 peer-reviewed publications to identify and assess ten recurring SaaS characteristics:

- subscription-based pricing models (Baur et al., 2024);
- scalability and flexibility (Blanco et al., 2023);
- multi-tenancy (Aleem et al., 2021; Blanco et al., 2023);
- use of service-level agreements (SLAs) (Sissodia, 2024);
- cloud infrastructure (George & Sagayarajan, 2023);
- continuous updates (Time et al., 2024);
- user experience design (Tello-Rodríguez et al., 2020; Harahap et al., 2024);
- data security and compliance (Humayun et al., 2022; George & Sagayarajan, 2023);
- customer support and training (Time et al., 2024);
- and performance monitoring and analytics (Candra et al., 2022).

These traits were selected for their recurrence in both foundational and recent SaaS literature. They represent the technical, operational, and user-facing dimensions that define SaaS systems in practice (Aleem et al., 2021; Blanco et al., 2023; Time et al., 2024), and provide a multidimensional lens for assessing cross-domain applicability to MaaS.

The objective is to understand how these SaaS traits are represented across the literature and to evaluate their potential translational value for manufacturing. Although SaaS principles are increasingly referenced in manufacturing environments, especially within the scope of Industry 4.0, their conceptual overlap with MaaS has not been systematically examined using bibliometric methods. A structured, data-driven mapping of this convergence can reveal the density, distribution, and thematic orientation of relevant research. To this end, we pose the guiding research question:

“To what extent can the key characteristics of SaaS be applied to or inform the development of MaaS?”

This study offers evidence to support researchers, practitioners, and policymakers in evaluating the translational potential of SaaS within cloud-enabled manufacturing systems. By focusing on architectural features and service delivery mechanisms, the analysis contributes to ongoing discussions on digital servitization and the evolution of industrial service ecosystems.

This paper is structured as follows: Section 2 outlines the research design, including selection parameters and filtering criteria. Section 3 presents the bibliometric results, followed by an analysis of SaaS characteristics in Section 4. Section 5 concludes with key findings and reflections from the assessment.

2 Bibliometric Research Framework

This section presents the methodological approach adopted for the bibliometric review, including database selection, search procedures, inclusion and exclusion criteria, and the analytical strategy employed to interpret the results.

2.1 Parameterization and Filtering Strategy

The dataset for this bibliometric analysis was retrieved exclusively from the Scopus database, selected for its broad disciplinary coverage—particularly in engineering, computer science, and industrial technology, which are central to both SaaS and MaaS research. Scopus is widely used in bibliometric studies due to its structured metadata, standardized indexing, and citation tracking features, supporting reproducibility and analytical consistency (Mongeon & Paul-Hus, 2016). Relying on a single, high-quality source also reduced formatting variability and minimized methodological noise in co-occurrence and citation analyses. An initial keyword-based search was conducted using the Boolean string:

("Software as a Service" OR SaaS) AND "cloud computing" AND ("digital manufacturing" OR implementation)

This query targeted publications explicitly referencing SaaS alongside cloud infrastructure and industrial digitalization. Including “implementation” or “digital manufacturing” helped focus the scope on practical deployment and contextual application, rather than purely conceptual discussions.

Filters were applied to include only peer-reviewed journal and conference articles written in English. The timeframe was limited to publications from 2014 onward to reflect the consolidation of SaaS as a mature paradigm and its structured application in industry. Pilot queries exploring earlier years returned results that lacked methodological alignment or clear integration of cloud-service logic.

Figure 1 summarizes the complete search structure and applied filters. The initial result set of 695 documents was reduced to 512 after removing duplicates and unrelated disciplinary content.

Fig. 1. Search Terms and Initial Filtering Process

A two-stage screening process followed (see Table 1). In Stage 1, documents were assessed through title and abstract screening using two guiding questions. Papers meeting at least one criterion advanced to full-text review, yielding 98 eligible entries. In Stage 2, full texts were evaluated using three questions. Papers answering at least two were retained, resulting in a final corpus of 65 documents.

Table 1. Exclusion Criteria

	Criteria Questions	Selection Criteria	Remaining Documents
Stage 1. Title and Abstract Reading	a) Does the abstract mention any SaaS/Cloud Computing characteristics cited in the introduction? b) Does the paper suggest the use or creation of a framework or process for SaaS implementation	One positive answer required	98 papers
Stage 2. Full Text Reading	a) Are the SaaS characteristics included in their methodology? b) Is any specific SaaS technology or architecture detailed? c) Is application usage or the implementation process shown?	Two positive answers required	65 papers

The inclusion criteria were designed to align directly with the study’s objective: assessing how SaaS traits may inform MaaS development. Papers were selected if they explicitly referenced or operationalized one or more of the ten SaaS traits introduced earlier. This ensured conceptual and practical relevance, enabling a structured mapping of these traits and their potential applicability to cloud-enabled manufacturing contexts.

2.2 Attribute Mapping and Pattern Extraction

The selection of SaaS traits for coding was based on a synthesis of frequently cited characteristics in systematic SaaS reviews and domain-specific studies (e.g., Nadeem, 2022; Humayun et al., 2022). The final list balances theoretical generality and practical observability, covering infrastructure-level, interaction-level, and business-model-level

dimensions. This framing supported consistent identification across publications and enabled a structured comparison to MaaS attributes introduced in Section 2.3.

A coding protocol was developed to identify the presence or absence of each trait across the 65 selected documents. To ensure transparency and reproducibility, an internal codebook was created with operational definitions and inclusion criteria. Although conducted by a single researcher, this predefined framework minimized subjectivity and supported consistent interpretation. Traits were marked as present when specific keywords, architectural elements, or implementation narratives aligned with the criteria shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Operational Criteria Used to Identify SaaS Characteristics

SaaS Trait	Inclusion Criteria
Subscription-Based Pricing	Mentions of licensing models, usage-based billing, or subscription access (e.g., SaaS tiers, per-user pricing, monthly fees)
Scalability and Flexibility	References to elastic resource provisioning, dynamic user scaling, or modular deployment capabilities
Multi-Tenancy Architecture	Descriptions of shared software instances, isolated user environments, or architectural designs enabling multiple tenants
Service-Level Agreements (SLAs)	Explicit mention of contractual service guarantees, availability metrics, uptime percentages, or user expectations
Cloud Infrastructure	Reference to hosting in cloud environments (e.g., IaaS/PaaS dependency), distributed computing, or public/private cloud support
Continuous Updates	Indications of versioning, automatic system upgrades, CI/CD pipelines, or agile update strategies
User Experience (UX) and Interface Design	Mentions of UI features, accessibility, customization options, or usability feedback mechanisms
Data Security and Compliance	Coverage of security protocols, encryption, regulatory standards (e.g., GDPR), or identity management systems
Customer Support and Training	Reference to onboarding materials, support centers, helpdesk, or customer education components
Performance Monitoring and Analytics	Indicators of tracking systems, dashboards, KPIs, or runtime diagnostics used for performance evaluation

Each paper was manually coded for the ten traits, enabling both frequency analysis and co-occurrence mapping. The latter was used to construct an enabler-strength network, visualizing how often traits co-appear in the literature. This network reveals interdependencies that can inform the theoretical integration of SaaS principles into MaaS frameworks.

To promote transparency and replication, the reviewed documents, coding results, and analysis outputs are available via Zenodo (Assef et al., 2024). For clarity and ease of comparison with manufacturing contexts, the SaaS traits were also grouped thematically, as shown in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. Categorization of SaaS Characteristics across Technical, Operational, and Business Lay-

2.3 Characterization of Manufacturing as a Service (MaaS) Principles

To enable a meaningful comparison between Software-as-a-Service (SaaS) and Manufacturing-as-a-Service (MaaS), it is essential to ground the analysis in a structured understanding of the latter. While SaaS is conceptually mature, MaaS remains an evolving construct within the broader digital transformation of manufacturing. Drawing from key literature on cloud manufacturing, cyber-physical systems, and digital servitization, this section synthesizes six recurring traits associated with MaaS (Wu et al., 2013; Hasan & Starly, 2020; Pivoto et al., 2021; Chiappa et al., 2023):

- **Virtualized Production Resources:** MaaS platforms depend on the virtualization of physical assets, such as machines, robotics, and additive manufacturing systems, into interoperable digital entities that can be dynamically allocated and reconfigured (Wu et al., 2013).
- **On-Demand Service Access:** Users access production services via cloud interfaces, enabling remote configuration, scheduling, and execution of manufacturing tasks with high flexibility (Hasan & Starly, 2020).
- **Usage-Based Pricing Models:** Like SaaS, MaaS supports pricing schemes based on resource consumption or time allocation, offering scalable access, particularly for SMEs (Arioli et al., 2022).
- **Integration with IIoT and Cyber-Physical Systems:** MaaS relies on IIoT-enabled architectures to monitor and exchange real-time data across distributed manufacturing systems (Pivoto et al., 2021).
- **Service-Level Agreements and Quality Guarantees:** Emerging MaaS platforms may include SLAs to formalize performance benchmarks, uptime, and product quality standards (Tan et al., 2022).
- **Customizable User Interfaces for B2B Clients:** As industrial users operate in specialized contexts, MaaS platforms increasingly prioritize user-centered design and transparent configuration (Chiappa et al., 2023).

These traits serve as a conceptual anchor for the comparative analysis in later sections. Although MaaS draws inspiration from SaaS, its implementation is shaped by physical constraints, asset heterogeneity, and regulatory complexities absent from software-only domains. Understanding these distinctions is key to evaluating the scope and feasibility of adapting SaaS logic to manufacturing contexts.

3 Quantitative Insights of SaaS Characteristics

This section presents the results of a quantitative analysis of the 65 selected publications, focusing on the ten SaaS characteristics identified earlier. Each paper was assessed for the presence and co-occurrence of these traits, enabling evaluation of their individual prevalence and relational patterns (full analysis available in Assef et al., 2024). This mapping helps identify how SaaS principles are interpreted across the literature and to what extent they may inform Manufacturing-as-a-Service (MaaS) development.

The bibliometric approach adopted here offers a structured alternative to purely conceptual reviews, supporting the detection of thematic clusters, dominant traits, and research gaps. These results provide a foundation for future empirical and applied studies in service-oriented manufacturing.

3.1 Overview of Publication Trends

To contextualize the evolution of SaaS research in industrial domains, publication and citation trends were analyzed over the selected timeframe (Figure 3). Peaks in 2010 and 2019 reflect foundational and renewed scholarly interest, respectively. In particular, the five papers from 2019 have accrued over 200 citations, indicating a resurgence driven by evolving technological and industrial demands.

Fig. 3. Temporal and Geographic Distribution of SaaS Literature

Geographically, contributions are broadly distributed. China leads with 14 publications, reflecting its investment in cloud infrastructure and growing role in software innovation (Yu et al., 2016). The United States, Australia, and Germany follow with six publications each, demonstrating sustained engagement with service-oriented technologies (Marston et al., 2011). Research from India, Italy, Brazil, and Turkey further illustrates the global scope of SaaS discourse.

These temporal and spatial patterns highlight both the persistent relevance of SaaS and its increasing importance in recent literature. The next section builds on this foundation by analyzing the content of selected publications to extract and categorize the core traits of SaaS research, establishing a conceptual basis for evaluating their transferability to MaaS contexts.

3.2 SaaS Attributes: Frequency and Connections Explored

This analysis aimed not only to describe SaaS literature but to identify which traits are most conceptually developed and widely adopted in practice. Understanding the frequency and co-occurrence of these traits helps assess their potential transferability to the Manufacturing-as-a-Service (MaaS) context.

We examined 65 peer-reviewed publications, focusing on ten core SaaS characteristics. The analysis captured both the frequency of individual traits and their co-occurrence patterns, offering insight into how SaaS principles are interpreted across the literature and how they might inform MaaS design.

All reviewed papers addressed at least three SaaS traits, indicating a prevalent multi-dimensional perspective (Figure 4). This reflects the understanding of SaaS as a holistic model, where technical, operational, and user-facing traits are treated as interdependent. The consistent co-occurrence of traits suggests that service effectiveness relies on a synergistic blend of infrastructure, usability, and trust-enabling features.

Fig. 4. Frequency of enablers and enablers per paper

Examining individual trait frequencies (Figure 5), three characteristics stand out: Cloud Infrastructure Development, Data Security and Compliance, and User Experience (UX) and Interface Design. Their prominence highlights the dual focus on technical robustness and user trust. In contrast, traits such as Service-Level Agreements (SLAs) and Customer Support appear less frequently, suggesting gaps in formal guarantees and post-deployment support.

Fig. 5. Overall enablers frequency

These trends suggest that interface and infrastructure elements of SaaS are mature and potentially translatable to MaaS platforms. Meanwhile, the lower presence of SLAs and support services indicates implementation challenges that should be addressed to improve reliability and client retention.

To explore interdependencies among traits, we constructed a co-occurrence network centered on individual enablers. Figure 6 illustrates the network for Data Security and Compliance, a highly connected trait often linked with Cloud Infrastructure and UX Design. This reinforces its role as a structural enabler in SaaS models. By contrast, Subscription-Based Pricing and Customer Support are more peripheral, signaling potential underexplored synergies (Assef et al., 2025).

Fig. 6. Data Security and Compliance network

To consolidate these insights, Table 3 presents a comparison of SaaS traits and their parallels—or gaps—within the MaaS context. This mapping highlights which principles translate directly, which require adaptation, and which remain conceptually underdeveloped.

Table 3. Comparative mapping of Software-as-a-Service (SaaS) and Manufacturing-as-a-Service (MaaS) traits

SaaS Characteristic	MaaS Parallel	Reference Support
Subscription-Based Pricing	Usage-based pricing models	Arioli et al. (2022); Hasan & Starly (2020)
Scalability and Flexibility	On-demand access to distributed production resources	Wu et al. (2013); Chiappa et al. (2023)
Multi-Tenancy Architecture	Facility/resource sharing with service-level differentiation	Hasan & Starly (2020)
Service-Level Agreements (SLAs)	SLAs for quality, uptime, and performance guarantees	Tan et al. (2022)
Cloud Infrastructure	Integration with IIoT and cyber-physical systems	Pivoto et al. (2021); Yang et al. (2020)
Automatic Updates / Continuous Improvement	Predictive maintenance and adaptive scheduling	Haghnegahdar et al. (2022); Yang et al. (2022)
UX and Interface Design	Customizable B2B interfaces and configuration platforms	Chiappa et al. (2023); Harahap et al. (2024)
Data Security and Compliance	Factory-level cybersecurity and IP protection	Mullet et al. (2021); Humayun et al. (2022)
Customer Support and Training	User onboarding and platform assistance for industrial clients	Time et al. (2024)
Performance Monitoring and Analytics	Real-time production feedback and traceability tools	Candra et al. (2022); Yang et al. (2020)

Identifying these gaps is essential for guiding the systematic design of MaaS platforms that reflect the complexity of industrial environments. A service model that mirrors the interconnected, security-driven, and user-focused logic of SaaS may enable greater resilience, scalability, and adoption in manufacturing systems.

These findings underscore the globally integrated and conceptually layered nature of SaaS research. With significant contributions from China, the United States, Australia, and Germany, the field demonstrates sustained international engagement. The recurring emphasis on infrastructure, user experience, and security further affirms that SaaS systems derive strength from well-aligned, co-evolving traits.

Beyond mapping current trends, this analysis lays the conceptual foundation for adapting SaaS principles to manufacturing. In the next section, we explore how these findings can support practical frameworks for MaaS deployment.

4 Discussion

When translated into the manufacturing domain, these findings highlight several implementation priorities. First, investment in digitally integrated infrastructure—supported by technologies like the Industrial Internet of Things (IIoT) and cyber-physical systems—is essential for enabling scalable MaaS platforms (Pivoto et al., 2021).

While this study did not isolate strictly MaaS-labeled publications, many reviewed works engage with cloud manufacturing and digital servitization contexts, demonstrating concrete applications of SaaS principles. For instance, Hasan and Starly (2020) describe a decentralized cloud architecture that mirrors multi-tenancy through configurable digital assets, while Chiappa et al. (2023) emphasize the importance of user-centric platform design for industrial B2B settings. These examples reinforce the practical relevance of SaaS traits in manufacturing and support the conceptual links surfaced in the bibliometric analysis.

Second, robust data security protocols remain critical for protecting production-sensitive information and establishing user trust (Mullet et al., 2021). Third, user-friendly interfaces enhance interaction with manufacturing services and respond to the market demand for customizability and transparency (Chiappa et al., 2023).

Other traits, such as performance monitoring, scalability, and continuous improvement, also align with manufacturing goals like predictive maintenance and agile responsiveness (Yang et al., 2020; Yang et al., 2022; Haghnegahdar et al., 2022). Although multi-tenancy presents physical implementation challenges, it can be conceptually adapted through shared-facility models that maintain service-level differentiation (Hasan & Starly, 2020).

Pricing models based on subscriptions or usage offer pathways to democratize advanced manufacturing access, particularly for SMEs (Arioli et al., 2022). Meanwhile, customer support and SLAs play a critical role in promoting user engagement and accountability yet remain underrepresented in existing MaaS literature (Tan et al., 2022).

Beyond these core traits, three critical gaps deserve attention. First, the evolution of business models, including value capture, revenue sharing, and service ownership, is central to sustaining MaaS in hybrid B2B ecosystems (Vendrell-Herrero et al., 2017; Coreynen et al., 2017). Second, communication costs (e.g., latency, bandwidth pricing) may limit the feasibility of fully virtualized networks (Wu et al., 2013; Yaqoob et al., 2017). Third, integration with legacy systems introduces architectural, security, and interoperability challenges that have received limited scholarly attention.

The co-occurrence network further clarified how SaaS traits relate conceptually and operationally. Some traits, like performance monitoring and multi-tenancy, could be jointly examined to better understand trade-offs between resource efficiency and service quality. Similarly, exploring how modular delivery models and continuous updates could be hybridized in transitional manufacturing environments may expand MaaS applicability.

Despite growing references to SaaS in manufacturing research, this conceptual transfer remains fragmented. Most studies focus on individual traits or isolated case applications, with limited attempts to build integrated frameworks for MaaS design. This underscores the need for more deliberate interdisciplinary collaboration—particularly

between information systems, industrial engineering, and operations management researchers.

5 Conclusion

This study employed a bibliometric analysis to examine how ten core SaaS characteristics are represented in the literature and to assess their applicability to Manufacturing-as-a-Service (MaaS). Findings from 65 publications highlight a strong emphasis on cloud infrastructure, data security, and user experience—suggesting these traits are foundational to reliable, scalable digital service platforms.

By synthesizing recurring concepts across SaaS literature, this study offers a structured, data-informed perspective on the conceptual bridge between SaaS and MaaS. It identifies shared attributes, highlights underexplored areas, and proposes a pathway for theoretical integration and practical adaptation. As cloud paradigms increasingly shape industrial production, aligning digital architectures with physical manufacturing systems becomes central to building scalable, resilient, and user-centered service models.

To support this transition, the paper proposes a SaaS-inspired capability framework organized into three functional layers: (1) infrastructure and system architecture, (2) service delivery and operations, and (3) user/business interface. For example, cloud infrastructure and data security form the technical base; continuous updates, SLAs, and performance monitoring enable service reliability; while UX design, pricing models, and training enhance user accessibility and satisfaction (Figure 7).

Fig. 7. SaaS-Inspired Layered Framework for Translating Digital Service Traits to MaaS Environments

The study's contribution lies not in introducing new SaaS technologies, but in systematically compiling and reorganizing existing knowledge to support translational use.

In fast-evolving domains, such syntheses are essential where conceptual borrowing often outpaces methodological clarity

5.1 Future research

To support future inquiry and address the conceptual and operational gaps identified in this study, Table 4 outlines suggested research directions. These priorities focus on refining MaaS models, addressing integration challenges, and advancing service-oriented architectures for cloud-enabled manufacturing.

Table 4. Future work suggestions

Theme	Observed Gap	Suggested Research Direction
Integration frameworks	Lack of conceptual bridges between SaaS architecture and manufacturing service delivery	Develop theoretical models that adapt SaaS layers (e.g., application, platform, infrastructure) to MaaS ecosystems
Multi-tenancy in physical environments	Physical constraints in applying multi-tenancy to manufacturing	Design hybrid facility-sharing models that enable service-level customization while maintaining operational efficiency
Data governance and cybersecurity	Few MaaS-specific discussions on data protection standards	Propose governance models addressing security, compliance, and liability in cloud-based manufacturing
UX in industrial contexts	Limited focus on user-centered interfaces for B2B industrial clients	Investigate how SaaS-style UX principles can improve accessibility, customization, and transparency in MaaS platforms
SLA performance in manufacturing	Underexplored application of service-level agreements in physical production environments	Develop SLA frameworks tailored to operational KPIs, downtime thresholds, and shared infrastructure usage
Empirical validation	Conceptual dominance without applied evaluation	Conduct case studies and pilot projects testing SaaS-based MaaS implementations in different sectors (e.g., automotive, medical devices)

This paper contributes to the literature by offering a structured, data-informed overview of the conceptual proximity between SaaS and MaaS. It identifies key attributes, uncovers underexplored intersections, and proposes a pathway for theoretical integration and practical adaptation. As cloud paradigms increasingly shape industrial production, aligning service-oriented digital architecture with physical manufacturing processes may become central to enabling more scalable, resilient, and client-responsive service models. The insights presented here aim to support both academic inquiry and practical strategy in the evolution of digitally enabled manufacturing ecosystems.

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